

Early Form of Writing Indonesian Popular Novel Stories 2000's Era

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Abstract

Popular novels are novels that people like. Popular novels cannot be separated from popular culture. Usually, popular novels achieve high sales. In this era of digital development, the way stories are told in novels is also developing, for example involving technology in the story. Such things need to be researched. Practically, the results of this research can contribute to creative writing. This research produces a conceptual theory and writing style of popular novels.

Keywords: *Early Forms of Stories, Popular Indonesian Novels, 2000s Era*

INTRODUCTION

Writing is an active, productive and creative activity. Alwasilah (1994: 78) argues that writing is a psycholinguistic process, starting from formulating ideas through semantic rules, then organizing them using syntactic rules, then presenting them in a writing system. Writing is a creative activity. Creativity is known as a higher order thinking activity. Creativity is the ability or finding new ways to solve problems, whether related to science, literary arts, or other fields.

Sibrani (2007) states that writing skills are the most difficult language skills to master because there are very complicated cognitive processes. Writing skills result from a combination of language skills, thinking, and understanding of forms/types of writing, for example fiction or non-fiction. Kinoysan (2009: 21) points out that the main key that must be prepared for writing is that you must have good ideas. Ideas can be obtained from your own experience, the experiences of other people, and readers. In the creative process of finding/determining ideas, we also need to read many works so that we can find unique ways of telling stories. That way, we can present the novel in a unique way.

There are many books on how to write fiction, including novels. However, the contents of these books are just writing tips and how to write novels consistently. These books do not discuss the novel writing model. In fact, if we write using a unique writing model, the writing can attract readers because it is easy to read and easy to understand.

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KKBI), form is curved, flexible, image, appearance, form, system or arrangement. In this research, form is defined as the shape or arrangement displayed in the novel, specifically at the beginning of the story. So, the shape referred to in this research is not the shape of an object, curved, convex, or so on. The form in this research can be interpreted as the writing style or the author's style of opening the story.

Adi (2011: 7) states that popular novels are proven to be more popular with the public. According to Dejawati (2021), popular novels developing in Indonesia are dominated by popular literature for teenage readers, including chick lit and teen lit. Popular novels are like

popcorn philosophy: popular, light, sweet, not filling, but selling. Therefore, popular novels are interesting to examine in terms of writing style.

In this era of digital development, the way stories are told in novels is also developing. These things need to be researched, how to start the story, what the plot is, what form the moral message is delivered in, and so on. This is in line with Siswantoro (2005: 21) who states that literary works are born from the process of absorbing the reality of human experience. As time goes by, the way stories are told in novels also continues to develop.

As a skill, writing is a combination of various things, namely: a combination of knowledge, abilities and opportunities (situations and conditions for writing). Therefore, it is necessary to know popular novel writing models to find uniqueness. Each novel author has his own way of telling the story. It is the author's creativity to obtain unique writing in building a story. As a beginner writer, it is best to learn from authors whose novels are sought after by many readers. Beginning writers can learn how authors convey their stories in various styles.

Popular novels cannot be separated from popular culture. According to Dejawati (2021), popular boundaries are popular experiences that are supported by information technology. Popular art survives because of the culture of consumption supported by the media. The media and the rise of consumers have shifted social ties which previously emphasized moral and cognitive aspects with aesthetic ties. Adi (2011: 20) states that novels are said to be popular because their themes, the way they present language techniques, and their writing follow general patterns that are popular with the reading public. In order not to be out of date and keep up with developments in the world of literature, it is important to research popular novel writing models.

Noor (2019) in his research stated that popular novels in terms of form have the same characteristics as popular art. These characteristics are simple, schematic or patterned, unambiguous, enjoyed, and not understood. The contents of popular novels have characteristics, namely: (1) entertainment means fun and full of beauty, (2) sentimental means the reader is carried away by feelings but does not experience them excessively, and (3) escapist art means the reader escapes into a fantasy world, full of dreams, a pleasant wish. Recent era novels are new or modern novels. Popular novels of the current era are novels that describe modern culture and are famous or popular today, not novels that were famous in the past.

The popular form of novel writing has never been studied. Of the books circulating in bookstores containing how to write stories, none of them explains in detail the model for writing popular novels. In fact, popular novels are influential in the development of the world of fiction. This can be proven from reader acceptance which can be seen from the level of sales and adaptation from other forms. That is the motivation for this research to be carried out.

This article is literary research. The aim is to describe the beginning of the story of a popular Indonesian novel from the 2000s. Practically, the results of this research can contribute to creative writing. This research produces a conceptual theory and writing style. This theory can be used by undergraduate students of Language and Literature Education as a guide for writing novels. The results of this research can also be used by lecturers to teach novel or story writing courses. This research is also useful for novice writers or writers who do not come from a language and literature educational background. This research can be used as a guide to writing novels with varying styles.

POPULAR NOVEL CRITERIA

Novels are narrative stories. Novels develop from non-fiction narrative forms, for example letters, biographies, chronicles or histories. Nurgiantoro (2015: 19) states that novels develop from documents and stylistically emphasize the importance of detail and are mimetic. Novels refer to higher realities and deeper psychology. According to Siswanto (2013: 127), novels are a form of modern fictional prose.

The development of the novel continues to progress from time to time. Each novel represents the spirit of each era in which it appears. Novels that are popular with the reading public, especially teenagers, are popular novels. Adi (2011: 20) states that novels are said to be popular in part because their themes, the way they present language techniques, and their writing follow general patterns that are popular with the reading public. The main means of the emergence of popular literature is language because in this language novels are read by many people. So, it can be concluded that popular novels are novels that are consumed by many people.

Nurgiantoro (2015) stated that popular novels are easier to read and easier to enjoy because they simply tell stories. Popular novels do not make pretensions or pursue aesthetic effects, but instead provide direct entertainment from the action of the story. The problems told are light, but actual and interesting, which is seen only in the same problem: romantic love (perhaps with a bit of a pornographic smell) with a model of life in a luxurious atmosphere. The novel tells the story of a love between a handsome man and a beautiful woman, able to lull teenage readers who are experiencing a sensitive period and can forget for a moment the bitterness of life that they experience in real life.

Popular novels pursue readers' tastes more, commercially. Popular novels don't tell anything serious because that would reduce the number of fans. Therefore, the language used is easy to understand, the plot is deliberately kept smooth and simple. The popularity of a novel can be seen from high sales.

EARLY FORM OF INDONESIAN POPULAR NOVEL STORIES IN THE 2000S ERA

The initial form of the story in the novel varies. The beginning of the story is the opening. A novel that has an interesting beginning, of course readers will like or be interested in reading the novel. The following is the initial form of the story of a popular Indonesian novel from the 2000s.

Description of More than One Character

The beginning of a story in the form of a description of more than one character is the beginning of a story that describes the character of the character, more than one character being described. The description involves explaining each character's physical characteristics, personality, and role in a narrative.

An example is the novel *Dilan: Dia adalah Dilanku Tahun 1990*, by Pidi Baiq which was published in 2014. This novel has the beginning of the story in the form of a description of more than one character. First, the beginning of the story describes the character of Aku or Milea. Second, the beginning of the story describes Milea's mother, Marissa Kusumarini. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

My name is Milea. Milea Adnan Hussain. Female gender, and just finished eating an orange. My last name is taken from my father's name. Someone I admire, and he is a TNI Army soldier. He was born in Batusangkar, Tanah Datar Regency, West Sumatra.

My mother, her name is Marissa Kusumarini, is usually called Icha by her friends. He's the mojang of Bandung born in Buah Batu.
(Baiq, 2014)

Atmosphere Description

Atmosphere description is a description of the atmosphere or feelings that are present in a certain place or situation. Atmosphere descriptions focus more on how a particular mood or feeling is affected by elements, such as lighting, weather, or a character's emotional state. The purpose of atmosphere description is to provide a clear and detailed picture so that readers or listeners can feel or imagine the atmosphere.

So, the beginning of the story in the form of a description of the atmosphere is a novel that opens with a description of the feelings present in a certain place or situation. An example is the novel *Padang Bulan*, by Andrea Hirata, which was published in 2010. This novel is an excerpt from the novel.

Syalimah was happy because her husband said he would give her a surprise gift. Syalimah couldn't stand it. (Hirata, 2010)

Setting Description

Setting description is a description of the place, time, and social conditions in which a story or event occurs. The setting description aims to provide a clear context to the reader or listener so that they can understand and imagine the setting or atmosphere in the story. The main elements in setting descriptions include place (physical setting) and time (temporal setting). Setting (physical setting) is a description of the location or physical environment where the story takes place, including geographical details, buildings, nature and surrounding objects. Temporal setting is a description of the time period of the story, which can be a specific time (hour, day, month, year) or historical era (a certain era, season, or historical event).

An example is the novel *Sang Pemimpi*, by Andrea Hirata, which was published in 2006. The beginning of the story in the novel provides a detailed description of the physical environment. The settings depicted include land sticking out of the earth, a split sky, the coast, a calm but oil-covered sea, and an elongated pier. These are all elements of place that help readers imagine the physical location of the story. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

Table of Contents this land sticks out from the bowels of the earth like land that has been hit by a powerful cataclysmic force. Bubbling because lava overflows beneath it. Then soaring above him, the sky split in two. In one part of the sky, the low sun reflected sticky steam trapped in a pitch-black cloud that had been covering the coast since morning. Meanwhile on the other side, ultraviolet bursts danced over the muted, oil-covered sea surface, orange like church windows, surrounding the pier that jutted out into the sea like a reign of fire, a circle of fire. And here, in this corner of the dock, in a strange room, I am confined, trapped, numb. (Hirata, 2006)

Description of Characters and Setting

The beginning of the story in the form of a description of the characters and setting is a novel that opens with a description of the characters and setting, be it the setting of place or setting of time or one of these two things. Character description is a description of the traits or personality, physical appearance, behavior and background of the characters in a story. Setting description is a description of the place, time, and social conditions in which a story or event occurs.

An example is the novel entitled *Selena*, by Tere Liye, which was published in 2020. The beginning of the novel opens with the introduction of a character named Selena and describes the birthplace of the character named Selena. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

My name is Selena.

I was born in the Sixth Crescent District, two hundred kilometers north of Tishri City, Moon Clan. It is not a developed and sophisticated area. It's a slum area, dense and underdeveloped. I was an orphan since childhood. My parents are corn farmers. My father died when I was fourteen years old, due to a serious illness. He has a congenital disease, he has been suffering from it since childhood. Our family was poor, we couldn't afford to take Dad to Tishri City Advanced Treatment Center. (Liye, 2020)

Scene Description

Scene description is a way of describing certain events or occurrences in a story in detail, including the action, dialogue, atmosphere and setting that existed at that time. The goal is to give readers a clear picture so they can imagine and feel the event as if they were there.

An example is the novel *Komet Minor*, by Tere Liye, which was published in 2019. The novel begins with a scene of Beth contemplating. Max, the trickster is waiting on Sunday Island. On the boat, Seli stopped crying. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

The sea surface is increasingly boiling. Beth looked around, It's only a matter of seconds now, the portal to the Minot Comet Clan will open. Max, aka the Crownless, aka the trickster, stands waiting on Sunday Island—an island with strange trees whose fruit has ripened after a vegetative-generative process of two thousand years.

On the boat, Seli had stopped crying, but was still very disappointed. I'm also disappointed, we have been completely cheated and trapped. We couldn't do anything, our bodies were bound by a silver net. But Ali didn't. Who knows what he was doing, suddenly he stopped shouting angrily at the Crownless. (Liye, 2019)

Object Description

Object description is a way of describing an object in detail so that readers or listeners can understand and imagine the object clearly. This description may include physical appearance, function, texture, color, size, and other relevant characteristics. The purpose of an object description is to provide a complete and accurate description of the object.

Physical appearance descriptions are descriptions of visual characteristics such as shape, color, and size. Function description is explaining the use or purpose of the object. Texture description is a description of how the object feels when touched. Material description is a

description of the composition of the object. Circumstance is a description of the current condition of the object. Specific or unique details are depictions of special characteristics that other objects do not have.

An example is the novel entitled *Bilangan Fu*, by Ayu Utami, published in 2008. The novel begins with a description of a jar of jam. The jar contains a segment. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

Bet. You'd be reluctant to believe me if I told you there was a jam jar containing a piece of pinkie joint. I got it from winning bets. I'm not crazy about that thing: a glass bottle containing a book with nails floating in formalin water. My girlfriend Marja hated him until he left. He said the thick, convex glass creates an aquarium effect. The little finger looks like a balakutak. Her purple nails were bruised eyes, catching him every time he glanced at them. I said, if you're afraid, don't look at him. I myself enjoy that pinky as one of the collection of objects I got from winning bets. (Utami, 2008)

Situation Description

Situation description is a depiction of what is happening in a particular event or scene. Situation descriptions provide details about activities, events, or interactions between characters in the context of a certain time and place, for example a situation description can describe a conversation between two characters in a room.

An example of a novel that begins with a description of the situation is the novel *Rantau Muara*, by A. Fuadi, published in 2013. The novel begins with a situation that is rushed and stuck. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

I plugged in the key and opened the door hastily. Congested. Not moving. Only other keys jangled and jangled. I dropped my fat backpack which was as heavy as a rock onto the floor, then I tilted my body and pushed the door with my shoulder. Bruk. The plywood door painted estuary blue finally shifted with a shuffling sound. The hinges are whining about lack of oil. For some reason, in every boarding house I've rented in this city, the size of the frame and door rarely match. (A. Fuadi, 2013)

Emotion Description

Emotional description is the ability to express or explain the feelings a person experiences. It involves using words, body language, facial expressions, and even tone of voice to communicate what a person is feeling at any given time. Emotional descriptions allow people to share their experiences with others, whether in the form of direct conversation, writing, art, or other mediums. This is important in building emotional connections, understanding oneself, and strengthening interpersonal relationships. An example of a novel that begins with a description of emotions is *Asmaraloka* by Arata Kim, published in 2021. The novel begins with emotions because things can be made practical, but are still complicated. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

IN this age of practicality, in fact there are still many troublesome things. For example, there is a minimarket door with one side that needs to be pushed and the other side pulled, but there is no information given as to which one needs to be pushed or pulled. If an ordinary glass door is easier, why use a door like that? In fact, it makes you in a bad mood in the morning. Even though my intention was only to buy bread, not to make life difficult. (Kim, 2021)

Previous Story Description

The description of the previous story is a summary or brief explanation of what happened in the previous story. This may be a plot overview, character introduction, or other important context that allows the reader or listener to understand what has happened previously in the narrative. Descriptions of previous stories are often used in serials or stories that have many parts, helping readers to recall previous events and understand their connection to the current part of the story.

The beginning of the story, which is in the form of a description of the previous story, is the novel *Jingga dalam Elegi*, by Esti Kinasih, which was published in 2011. The novel explains the previous story, namely the character Ari, the troublemaker who keeps a secret. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

Previous Story...

Ari, or in full Matahari Senja, is the troublemaker at Airlangga High School. He has a series of bad reputations and a violation of a series of rules. He kept a secret, because he let no one know where he lived.

(Kinasih, 2011)

Time and Situation Description

Time is a concept used to measure the change, sequence, and duration of events. It is the dimension within which events occur, take place, or are organized. The concept of time can vary depending on the context, such as physical time in physics, chronological time in history, subjective time in individual experience, and so on. A situation is a description of activities, events, or interactions between characters in the context of a certain time and place, for example a situation description can describe a conversation between two characters in a room.

The beginning of the story in the form of a description of time and situation is the beginning of the story which describes a combination of time and situation. An example of a novel that begins with a description of the time and situation is *Cinta Paling Rumit* by Boy Candra in 2018. The novel begins with a description of the time at three in the afternoon. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

At three in the afternoon at a fast food place, I was waiting for someone. Thirty minutes passed. I already finished half the glass of moeca float. I haven't ordered food yet. Apart from not being too Japanese, I want to eat alone with him. He must also be hungry and waiting for the time to eat with me. So, it would be selfish if I ate first without him. (Candra, 2018)

Character Description in Biodata Format

A character description in biodata format is a comprehensive description of who the character is, his background, personality, skills, and interests and hobbies in the form of biodata. An example of a novel that begins with a character description in biodata format is the novel *Off the Record*, by Ria SW, published in 2018. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

Introduction

Do you remember what happened when you were four years old? Actually, this is the most exciting part for flashbacks to childhood.

Hi! I:

Favorite Movie/Show:

Favorite Game:

Ambition:

Well, now it's my turn, okay?

Hi! I'm Ria SW

Favorite Movie/Show: MT vit

Favorite Game:

Playing drums using Khong Guan biscuit tins. Playing with plasticine candles and molding them into tins

Hi! I

Goals: Many!

Well, this is the beginning of a life full of "accidents and My accident."

(Ria SW, 2018)

Motivation

Motivation is the drive or reason that drives someone to take action or achieve certain goals. Novels that begin with motivation are novels that provide advice or encouragement to readers to take better action. An example of a novel that begins with motivation is *Ranah 3 Warna*, by A. Fuadi, published in 2011. The novel begins with the motivation of patience and sincerity. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

Be patient and sincere in every step of your actions
Continuously do good, both in your village and abroad
stay away from bad deeds and know that the perpetrators will definitely be punished
in the bowels of the earth and on the earth
A. Fuadi, 2011)

Prologue Description Introduction

The beginning of the story in the form of a prologue, an introductory description, is a novel that opens with a prologue or introduction before entering the actual story. An example is the novel *Ancika: Dia yang Bersamaku Tahun 1995*, by Pidi Baiq, which was published in 2021. The novel begins with a prologue before entering the real story. The prologue contains a description of the story that will be shared in the novel. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

The story I will share starts from my teenage years, 24 years ago. This is not an extraordinary story, but it is a true story about me, which I experienced directly with a man named Dilan. It was a time and memory of bitter sweet moments from both of our pasts. And actually this story is also about how I found myself.
(Baiq, 2021)

Poetry Prologue

The beginning of the story in the form of a poetic prologue is a novel that opens with an introduction containing poetry. An example of a novel that has the initial form of a story in the form of a prologue describing the situation is the novel *Laut Bercerita*, by Leila S. Chudori, published in 2017. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

You die
You will be born many times...

The poet once wrote a line of this poem on a scrap shabby paper. At that time he still had long hair reaching out shoulders and had a hoarse voice because he gave many speeches in front of workers. He slipped it into a black-covered notebook and said it was a gift from him for my 25th birthday.
(Chudori, 2017)

Narrative Description Prologue

A narrative description prologue is an introduction or opening in a story that provides an initial description of the setting, atmosphere, characters, or main theme. The goal is to interest the reader and provide the context necessary to understand the story being told. This prologue usually contains narrative elements that are told in a descriptive style and inspire the imagination.

The novel that begins with a narrative description prologue is the novel *99 Cahaya di Langit Europa*, by Hanum Salsabiela Rais and Rangga Almahendra, published in 2014. This novel provides an initial description of the feelings of my character who lives in Europe. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

Living in Europe for 3 years became an arena for exploring Europe and everything in it. For the first time in 26 years, I experienced living in a country where Muslims were a minority. An experience that further enriches the spiritual dimension to get to know Islam in a different way. This book is a travelogue of a quest. (Rais and Almahendra, 2014)

Prologue Description of Atmosphere

An atmosphere description prologue is an introduction to a story that describes the atmosphere or feelings that exist in a certain place or situation. Atmosphere descriptions focus more on how a certain atmosphere or feeling is influenced by elements such as lighting, weather, or a character's emotional state, for example atmosphere descriptions can create an image of an eerie atmosphere in a dark forest at night.

An example of a novel that begins with a prologue describing the atmosphere is *Autumn in Paris*, by Ilana Tan, published in 2007. The novel describes the atmosphere of quiet streets and strong winds. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

THE STREETS are quiet.
Dark sky.
The autumn wind blew hard.
He tightened the jacket he was wearing, but his body was still shivering. Not because of the wind, because right now he couldn't feel anything at all. It seems like his nerves are no longer functioning. He couldn't see, couldn't hear, couldn't make a sound, and couldn't feel anything. Except for the pain in his heart. He could feel that one. It really hurts....
(Tan, 2007)

Advice Prologue

An advice prologue is an introductory part in a work that contains a message or advice given to the reader. Such prologues are often found in works that have an educational or moral purpose. An advice prologue can be a suggestion, hint, or thought that will hopefully provide the reader with guidance on how to deal with life or a particular situation.

An example of a novel that begins with a prologue of advice is *Let It Flow*, by Mounalizza, published in 2022. The prologue of the novel provides advice about honesty and commitment. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

Prologue
Dishonest from the start,
So since then the commitment has been fragile....
(Mounalizza, 2022)

Dialogue and Description of Emotions

Dialogue is a conversation between two or more characters in a story. Good dialogue can reveal the characteristics, motivations and relationships between characters, as well as speed up the storyline. Emotional description is a way of describing a character's feelings through words. This can be done by depicting facial expressions, body language, or using narration to explain the character's feelings directly.

The beginning of the story in the form of dialogue and emotional descriptions is the beginning of the story which describes conversations and emotional descriptions. The novel that begins with dialogue and emotional descriptions is *Layangan Putus*, by Mommy ASF, published in 2020. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

“Tu kaaaan...”
I showed the results of the two-line testpack. “Here.” My feelings are mixed. Mas Aris stared
the test pack I gave him, he reflexively said, “Well...
So, what's next?”
“So what, so what! Yes, pregnant!”
I closed the bathroom door while grumbling.
Shock and anxiety surged within me.
This is my second pregnancy. My eldest Aamir just turned 10 months old. This pregnancy is too close.
I still dream of having a spontaneous birth, but the chances of that seem to be getting slimmer. I washed my hands in the sink, faced the mirror and let out a long sigh.
“Ouch....”
(Mommy ASF, 2022)

Short Message from Cell Phone

The beginning of the story in the form of a short message from a cell phone is the beginning of a story that describes messages from electronic mail, for example SMS and WhatsApp. An example of a novel that begins with a short message from a cell phone is *Love for Rent: Celebrity's Love Story*, by Jongchansshi. The following is an excerpt from the novel.

HB Creative Director Tasya

Mil, I'm really sorry about that in advance. Just received news from the boss that Mr. Gustav wanted Winda's character to be played by a newcomer, so we chose it from the results of the open casting. Sorry, Mil. Hopefully we can work together another time!

To HB Creative Tasya

Relax, sis. Nothing. I wish you success for your project!

Due to the frequent sudden contract cancellations in the last three months, Mila was no longer surprised when she read the messages from Tasya, staff at the production house handling the *Wasiat Nyi Rombeng* Film project.

(Jongchansshi)

Poetry

Poetry is a medium of expression that uses words in a creative and artistic way to convey ideas, feelings or experiences. Traditionally, poetry often uses structure, rhythm, rhyme, and metaphorical language to create a deep aesthetic experience for the reader or listener. In poetry, writers often play with sound, rhythm, and language to explore broad themes, from love and the beauty of nature to questions of philosophy and human struggle.

The novel that begins with poetry is the novel *My Ice Girl*, by Pit Sani, which was published in 2018. The novel opens with a poem entitled *Girl with Dimples*. An excerpt from the novel is as follows.

Dimpled Girl

Sometimes interest can arise from simple things

It's as simple as seeing the way you smile

You are here to change everything to be more beautiful

You take my love as high as the sky. Make me feel perfect

(Sani, 2018)

CONCLUSION

Writing is an active, productive and creative activity. The main key that a writer must prepare is a good idea. Ideas can be obtained from your own experience, the experiences of other people, and readers. In the creative process of finding/determining ideas, we also need to read many works so that we can find unique ways of telling stories. That way, we can present the novel in a unique way. Beginner novel writers can learn from popular novels that many people like. Beginner writers can get inspiration for writing, one of which is how to open or start writing. The initial writing must be unique and interesting because it is the reader's door.

The results of this research are variations in the initial form of popular Indonesian novel stories from the 2000s which can be used as inspiration for writing the first part of the story. The initial form of the novel's story is description, motivation, prologue, dialogue, short messages from cell phones, and poetry. Description consists of ten types, namely (1) description of more than one character, (2) description of atmosphere, (3) description of setting, (4) description of characters and setting, (5) description of objects, (6) description of situation, (7)) description of emotions, (8) description of previous story, (9) description of time and situation, (10) description of character in biodata format. Prologue consists of five types,

namely (1) introductory description prologue, (2) poetry prologue, (3) narrative description prologue, (4) atmosphere description prologue, and (5) advice prologue.

Reference

- 1) Ajidarma, Seno Gumira. 1992. *Asmaraloka*. Jakarta: Pustaka Firdaus.
- 2) Alwasilah, A. Chaedar. 1994. *Dari Cicalengka Sampai Chicago: Bunga Rampai Pendidikan Bahasa*. Bandung: Angkasa.
- 3) Ari, Kinoyasan. 2009. *Jadi Penulis Fiksi?*. Yogyakarta: CV Andi Offset.
- 4) ASF, Mommy. 2020. *Layangan Putus*. Jakarta: Falcon Publishing.
- 5) Baiq, Pidi. 2014. *Dilan: Dia adalah Dilanku Tahun 1990*. Bandung: Pastel Books.
- 6) Baiq, Pidi. 2019. *Cinta Paling Rumit*. Bandung: Pastel Books.
- 7) Baiq, Pidi. 2020. *Ancika: Dia yang Bersamaku Tahun 1995*. Bandung: Pastel Books.
- 8) Chudori, Leila S. 2017. *Laut Bercerita*. Jakarta: Kepustakaan Populer Gramedia.
- 9) Dewojati, Cahyaningrum. 2021. *Sastra Populer Indonesia*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- 10) Fuadi, Ahmad. 2009. *Ranah 3 Warna*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 11) Fuadi, Ahmad. 2020. *Rantau 1 Muara*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 12) Hirata, Andrea. 2006. *Sang Pemimpi*. Yogyakarta: Bentang Pustaka.
- 13) Hirata, Andrea. 2010. *Padang Bulan*. Yogyakarta: Bentang Pustaka.
- 14) Kinasih, Esti. 2007. *Love for Rent*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 15) Kinasih, Esti. 2011. *Jingga dalam Elegi*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 16) Liye, Tere. 2018. *Komet Minor*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 17) Liye, Tere. 2018. *Selena*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 18) Noor, R. (2019). *Ciri Intrinsik Novel Populer Indonesia yang Terbit Tahun 1980-an*. NUSA, 14(4), 454-464.
- 19) Novellina A. (2012). *My Ice Girl*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 20) Nurgiantoro, Burhan. 2015. *Teori Pengkajian Fiksi*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University press.
- 21) Rais, Hanum Salsabiela & Rangga Almahendra. 2011. *99 Cahaya di Langit Eropa: Perjalanan Menapak Jejak Islam di Eropa*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 22) Simamora, Christian. 2013. *Let It Flow*. Jakarta: GagasMedia.
- 23) Siswantoro. 2005. *Metode Penelitian Sastra: Analisis Psikologis*. Surakarta: Muhammadiyah University Press Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.
- 24) SW, Ria. 2016. *off the Record*. Jakarta: GagasMedia.
- 25) Tan, Ilana. 2007. *Autumn in Paris*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 26) Utami, Ayu. 2008. *Bilangan Fu*. Jakarta: Kepustakaan Populer Gramedia.